

Linking teachers' work engagement to shared leadership in school: The mediating role of teacher leadership

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Abstract: This research aims to determine the mediating role of teacher leadership in the relationship between teachers' work engagement and shared leadership. The study uses a quantitative research approach and follows a relational screening model. The study population consists of teachers working in Uşak, and the sample includes 476 teachers. In the data collection process, the Shared Leadership Perception Scale, Teacher Leadership Scale, and Work Engagement Scale were used. Based on the literature on the relationships between the research variables, a structural model was created and tested with the obtained data. According to the results of the study, there are positive moderate-level relationships between shared leadership in schools and teacher leadership. Teachers' perceptions of shared leadership significantly predict their work engagement. Teacher leadership plays a mediating role in predicting the level of work engagement through shared leadership. Based on these results, it can be suggested that to increase the work engagement of teachers, who play a key role in achieving the goals of schools, schools should integrate shared leadership into their structure and provide opportunities for teacher leadership.

Keywords: Shared leadership, work engagement, teacher leadership, school leadership, educational leadership, positive emotions toward work.

1. Introduction

Teachers play a key role in the achievement of educational goals in schools. Their work engagement shapes the way these roles are fulfilled. Work engagement is a mental state characterized by positive and satisfying emotions, vitality, and commitment related to work (Høigaard, Giske, & Sundsli, 2012; Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá & Baker, 2002; Hultell & Gustavsson, 2011). Employees who are engaged in their work experience positive emotions in the workplace, have the ability to activate organizational resources and potentials, and perform better (Gamero-Burón & Lassibille, 2018). Research has emphasized that work engagement, including gains such as increased morale, job satisfaction, motivation, improved interpersonal relationships, ownership of work, a sense of worth, and organizational commitment, is linked to shared leadership (Bligh, Pearce, Kohles, 2006; Li, Wang & Chen, 2008; Scott & Caress, 2005; Wood, 2005). Furthermore, studies in other organizations, such as those by Wood and Fields (2007), Black and Westwood (2004, cited in Kocolowski, 2010), Hulpia, Devos, and Rosseel (2009), and Gamero-Burón and Lassibille (2018), as well as research conducted in schools, have determined that shared leadership positively influences work engagement, which can be described as positive emotions toward work. Research studies conducted in Türkiye by Uslu and Beycioğlu (2013), Ağıroğlu Bakır and Aslan (2014), Sariçiçek (2014), Bostancı, Gidiş, Uğurlu and Dilsiz (2018), Yılmaz (2013) and Yener (2016) have also found that work engagement gains in schools are influenced by shared leadership practices. In this sense, it can be stated that shared leadership in schools affects teachers' work engagement.

In the OECD report, it is stated that shared leadership plays a crucial role in the achievement of school goals and student learning in the 21st century. In this context, distributed leadership theory emphasizes that school leadership is not exclusive to administrators; rather, it should be shared among teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders (Spillane, 2005). The distributed leadership approach contributes to school development by supporting capacity building through the participation of all stakeholders in management processes (Harris, 2004). This approach advocates for teachers' involvement in decision-making processes, the collective sharing of the school's vision, and the decentralization of leadership roles.

Therefore, within the scope of this study, the relationship between shared leadership and teacher leadership aligns with the fundamental assumptions of distributed leadership theory. Distributing leadership in this way holds the potential to enhance teachers' work engagement, job satisfaction, and motivation (Ereş & Akyürek, 2016; Kaplan & Yüner, 2023; Spillane, Halverson & Diamond, 2004; Uçar & Dağlı, 2017). Accordingly, it emphasizes the need to redefine school leadership beyond the authority of school principals, establish and support school boards for school management, and develop and promote leadership skills. Shared leadership in schools leads to better results in school success (OECD, 2016). Shared leadership is a dynamic, interactive influence process among individuals within a group to achieve a goal. This influence process generally involves peer or lateral influence, but also includes hierarchical influence that can be upward or downward (Pearce, Conger & Locke, 2007; Wu, Cormican & Chen, 2018). In the report of the School Leadership Development Conference held on April 9-10, 2009 in Türkiye, shared leadership's importance was highlighted by focusing on the changes in school leadership and the effects of those changes (MEB, 2011). However, despite the presence of teacher councils, subject teacher groups, and branch teacher councils aimed at shared leadership in the structure of schools in Türkiye, the centralized nature of the Ministry of National Education continues to have an impact. These councils are often limited to implementing directives from the ministry rather than going beyond that.

Shared leadership in schools also creates an environment for and supports teacher leadership (Cheng & Szeto, 2016; Southworth, 2008; Zepeda, Mayers & Benson, 2013; Uribe-Flórez, Al-Rawashdeh & Morales, 2014; Wilhelm, 2013; Lai, 2015). Research results have reflected that shared leadership in schools increases teachers' leadership skills (Harris & Muijs, 2004; Kocolowski, 2010; Slavit, Kennedy, Deuel & Nelson, 2011; Printy & Marks, 2006; Rice, 2006; Wu, Cormican & Chen, 2018). Teacher leadership is seen as a progressive path that can bring the dynamism necessary to improve the teaching-learning process and shift the teaching profession from being a tedious and passive job to an exciting endeavor (Nudrat & Akhtar, 2014). Research studies conducted by Gokhale (2015) and Sesen, Tabak and Arli (2017) have also found that teacher-leaders have more positive emotions toward their schools and work. The OECD reports that shared leadership in schools can help teachers become high-quality leaders, which will increase teachers' trust in one another and enable them to engage in more effective initiatives (OECD, 2016). It is stated that teacher-leaders demonstrate high school commitment, job satisfaction, self-assessment, self-motivation, and self-goal setting behaviors (Sesen, Tabak & Arli, 2017).

Therefore, it can be understood from the literature that teacher leadership plays a mediating role in the relationship between teachers' work engagement and shared leadership. In this study, a structural mediation model based on the literature on the relationships between the research variables will be tested. The scope of the research is to link teachers' work engagement to shared leadership in schools in Uşak, Türkiye, and determine the mediating role of teacher leadership. Based on the results obtained from the research, it is hoped that structural arrangements related to shared leadership will be present in the school environment for educational administrators and policymakers and that awareness will be created regarding providing opportunities for teacher leadership. In the following section, the variables of the study and the relationships between them are explained in more detail.

1.1. Shared Leadership

Shared leadership is a relational and collaborative leadership process in which employees influence each other and share tasks and responsibilities. In this sense, everyone within the organization is responsible for leadership, and leadership emerges through regular interactions among team members (Kocolowski, 2010; Lindsay, Day & Halpin, 2011). Shared leadership represents reciprocal influences that overcome the limitation of leadership style confined to a single leader within a team (Lee, Lee, Seo & Choi, 2015). It is an ongoing, simultaneous process of shared leadership within the team aimed at maximizing the team's potential, considering how specific leadership tasks can be shared among team members. In shared leadership, all employees are responsible for both teamwork and leadership behaviors (Muethel & Hoegl, 2013). Since shared leadership arises from the interactions among team members, all organizational employees share equal status and responsibility in leadership practices. Success and failure belong to all members (Bligh, Pearce & Kohles, 2006; Ensley, Hmieleski & Pearce, 2006; Ryan & Coglisier, 2011). Shared leadership is also regarded as a set of role functions that can be performed by any

member of the group. Therefore, shared leadership emphasizes the importance of discrete, collective, or reciprocal effects among multiple group members (Wu, Cormican & Chen, 2018). In shared leadership, participation in decision-making and goal setting by all members, along with the acceptance of responsibility for the outcomes of these decisions, fulfilling their responsibilities to achieve goals, and the distribution of autonomy and accountability among all individuals in the team, is necessary. In shared leadership, all school staff have a say in the fulfillment of any task (Wood, 2005). Since shared leadership involves a team composition, the attitudes of team members toward shared leadership and their willingness to share leadership responsibilities are considered important (Small, 2007). The effective emergence of shared leadership is not solely dependent on the distribution of tasks but is also directly related to the presence of an organizational climate that supports this form of leadership. Indeed, in their study conducted in public educational institutions, Carvalho, Sobral, and Mansur (2020) emphasize the necessity of a supportive organizational climate for the development of shared leadership. Their findings indicate that this leadership approach has positive effects in reducing turnover rates among public school teachers. For a school to effectively fulfill its mission, leadership must be shared across all areas with school staff, and every school employee must do their part in this shared responsibility (Bostanci, 2013). According to Hulpia, Devos, and Van Keer (2009), a school is a shared leadership team consisting of individuals with official leadership roles as a whole. Shared leadership in schools is described as a management practice that enables teachers to participate in the decision-making process and share in the implementation of these decisions; it is the result of the distribution of leadership influence among multiple team members, known as emergent team property leadership. Therefore, schools must develop or adopt modern leadership trends such as shared leadership in order to continue fulfilling their social and educational roles (Alanezi, 2016).

1.2. Teacher Leadership

Teacher leadership is a concept that has emerged based on distributed, shared, and collaborative leadership for school development. However, the distinction between the power dynamics of school leaders and teachers remains unclear, which hampers collaborative work and professional responsibility (Lowery-Moore, Latimer, & Villate, 2016; Flood & Angelle, 2017; Szeto & Cheng, 2017; King, 2017). Nevertheless, teacher leadership has been recognized as an important area of study for school development since the 1980s. It is seen as a continuously evolving leadership role where teachers lead not only in their classrooms but also to other teachers, students, and the curriculum, and schools demonstrate leadership for development. Additionally, teacher leadership contains synergistic elements for school development (Lowery-Moore, Latimer & Villate, 2016; Cherkowski & Schnellert, 2017; Szeto & Cheng, 2017). Recent studies have also demonstrated that teacher leadership directly influences teacher learning, and that this learning has an even greater impact on teachers' professional development (Pan & Chen, 2020). Teacher leadership activates the untapped potential of teachers and encompasses a broad scope, from school development to societal impact. The concept of teacher leadership transforms schools into professional learning communities (Cheng & Szeto, 2016; Szeto & Cheng, 2017). At the core of teacher leadership lies the idea of contributing to the transformation of schools into democratic environments (Beycioğlu & Aslan, 2012). Teacher leadership is seen as an intermediary structure between the school, classroom, and student outcomes (Sawyer, Neel & Coulter, 2016; Flood & Angelle, 2017). York-Barr and Duke (2004) explain teacher leadership in schools through five themes: 1) moving beyond the classroom walls with teacher leadership, 2) supporting professional learning in schools, 3) teachers' participation in decision-making in school management, 4) the improvement of student learning and achievement, and 5) working towards the development and change of the entire school. Harris and Muijs (2004) also list the benefits of teacher leadership as increasing school effectiveness, improving teacher effectiveness, and contributing to school development. Teacher leadership is defined as "the process by which teachers, individually or collectively, influence their colleagues, administrators, and other members of the school community to improve teaching and learning practices to enhance students' learning and achievement" (Uribe-Flórez, Al-Rawashdeh & Morales, 2014).

1.3. Work Engagement

Work engagement is defined as a positive and satisfying mood related to work. Employees who are engaged in their work exhibit high levels of energy, a willingness to focus on their tasks and dedication. Their work is passionate, prideful, and inspiring for them (Høigaard, Giske & Sundsli, 2012; Bakker & Bal, 2010; Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá & Bakker, 2002; Turgut, 2011; Hultell & Gustavsson, 2011). Most studies in the literature emphasize individual and job design-related factors as antecedents of work engagement in the public sector (Zahari & Kaliannan, 2022). Work engagement is seen in three ways: vigor, dedication, and absorption (Schaufeli & Salanova, 2007; Turgut, 2011; Iyer, 2016; Rothmann & Hamukang'andu, 2013). Vigor is related to high energy levels and resilience. It includes the employee's willingness to exert continuous effort in their work and their ability to avoid easily getting fatigued. When employees are dedicated to their work, it holds great importance for them, inspires them, and they take pride in it. They continue working with enthusiasm and perseverance despite challenges. Dedication reflects the importance and sense of belonging an individual feels toward their work. Absorption refers to a state of focus on the task at hand and overcoming obstacles or problems. Employees joyfully immerse themselves in their work, lose track of time, and struggle to take breaks from work (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003; Bakker & Bal, 2010; Schaufeli & Salanova, 2007; Turgut, 2011; Iyer, 2016). Engaged employees experience positive emotions in their organizations, have the ability to activate motivational resources, and perform better. Work engagement is a valuable indicator of both employees' and organizations' professional well-being (Gamero-Burón & Lassibille, 2018). In a study conducted by Bakker and Bal (2010) in schools, it was found that engaged teachers are more effective teachers (Choochom, 2016). Teachers who are engaged in their work also play a significant role in the development of the school. Work engagement fosters a sense of responsibility for high levels of job performance. A teacher's level of work engagement can be observed in four dimensions: emotional engagement, cognitive engagement, social engagement with colleagues, and engagement with students. Emotional engagement is defined as the teachers' enthusiasm, pride, and inspiration while performing their work and being at the workplace. Cognitive engagement refers to teachers' complete involvement in their work and their joyful immersion in it. Social engagement with colleagues describes the teacher's relationships with their colleagues in the workplace. Finally, student engagement refers to the relationships created through social interactions with students (Khan, 2016).

1.4. The Relationship Between Shared Leadership in Schools and Teachers' Work Engagement

In a study conducted in a school where shared leadership was implemented, it was found that teachers were more satisfied with their jobs (Hulpia, Devos & Rosseel, 2009). In organizations with shared leadership, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and job performance increase, while job stress, burnout levels, and serious conflicts decrease. It is suggested that administrators should strive to create a positive work environment where employees in the organization have a shared and common sense of purpose, support each other, recognize individual and team contributions, and proactively participate in decision-making and constructive discussions (Alanezi, 2016; Wu, Cormican & Chen, 2018). Another study conducted in public schools found that organizational culture is a significant predictor of teachers' level of work engagement (Khan, 2016). Positive emotions toward work in the organization visibly increase organizational commitment, organizational citizenship, and performance. Furthermore, establishing desired relationships with other employees, positively influencing others, and collaboration are all outcomes of positive emotions toward work (Staw, Sutton & Pelled, 1994). A culture of sharing in schools can also influence teachers' work engagement. School management styles have an impact on teachers' behaviors within the school. It has been found that shared leadership has a positive effect on teachers' behaviors at work and the development of effective schools (Alanezi, 2016). In shared leadership, involving teachers in decision-making processes has increased their organizational commitment levels, positively affecting job satisfaction, professional development, psychological capital, and motivation (Göktaş & Kaya, 2023).

1.5. *The Relationship Between Shared Leadership and Teacher Leadership in Schools*

The approach to shared leadership in the literature is seen as sharing leadership, reciprocal leadership in groups, bringing together leadership capacities at the top to guide others, and producing leadership through interaction (Mokoena, 2017). School leaders are expected to solve all the problems schools face, but in today's educational environment, it is almost impossible for a school leader to accomplish this without shared leadership practices. Additionally, the future demands on school leaders require them to know how to share leadership responsibilities in order to meet the needs of all stakeholders. By sharing leadership responsibilities, school leaders enhance the effectiveness of their professional community, which in turn increases school success. School and student success is more likely to emerge with shared leadership (York-Barr & Duke, 2004; Zepeda, Mayers & Benson, 2013; Wilhelm, 2013; Nappi, 2014). Teacher leadership is based on collaborative leadership behavior and the sharing of leadership between school leaders and teachers (Cheng & Szeto, 2016). Teacher leadership is considered essential for the development of schools (Kılınc & Receptoğlu, 2013). The success of the school depends on strong teacher leadership. The idea of having shared leadership is necessary to maximize teacher leadership. In schools, teacher capabilities are seen as a strong knowledge base for triggering change and development. In shared leadership, teachers and administrators can better serve teaching and learning in schools. This is because leadership in the school is seen as a shared responsibility (Uribe-Flórez, Al-Rawashdeh & Morales, 2014; Lai, 2015). In shared leadership, school staff collaborate to develop focused goals and plans to achieve them. In a school environment where shared leadership persists, teachers are encouraged to lead in the process of learning and change (Rice, 2006). Shared leadership is defined as a key governance foundation for the future, which allows school leaders to perform their roles more effectively through collaboration and teamwork, and provides ways to make schools manageable. In this way, there is a higher likelihood of creating a school culture where key stakeholders such as teachers, students, and parents willingly take responsibility for leading school communities (Mokoena, 2017).

1.6. *The Relationship Between Teacher Leadership and Work Engagement*

Teacher leadership is considered a valuable strategy for school development by activating teachers' potential and is seen as a necessary tool for empowering teachers and enhancing teacher professionalism (Cheng & Szeto, 2016; Supovitz, 2018). Leader teachers ensure the achievement of high-quality educational outcomes. These leader teachers are characterized by abilities and skills such as emotional stability, interpersonal skills, instructional competence, learning ability, collaboration, and entrepreneurship (Nudrat & Akhtar, 2014). As can be understood, teacher leadership can be stated to influence teachers' work engagement. In studies, leader teachers who take control of their work tend to engage more with their jobs. The achievement of the school's overall goals depends on teachers' competence and motivation in teaching and learning (Hauge, Norenes & Vedoy, 2014). In school environments, teachers who actively participate in learning and management processes tend to be more creative in improving their teaching skills and instructional performance (Bae, Song, Park & Kim, 2013). Engaged employees experience positive emotions in the workplace, have the ability to activate organizational resources and potentials and perform better. In schools with low teacher responsibilities and professional competencies, motivation and encouragement are often found to be low (Gamero-Burón & Lassibille, 2018). Therefore, teacher leadership practices that enhance teachers' work engagement and strengthen their active, physical, emotional, and cognitive aspects should be supported in schools (Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá & Bakker, 2002).

From the literature, it is evident that the research variables are interrelated. Therefore, the study aims to determine the mediating role of teacher leadership in the relationship between shared leadership in schools and teachers' work engagement. The constructed structural mediation model is tested with the following hypotheses:

H1: Shared leadership significantly positively predicts work engagement behavior.

H2: Teacher leadership plays a mediating role in the relationship between shared leadership in schools and teachers' work engagement.

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

The study aims to determine the mediating role of teacher leadership in linking teachers' work engagement to shared leadership in schools. The study follows a relational screening model. The structural mediation model of the research is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Structural Mediation Model of the Research

2.2. Population and Sample

The population of the research consists of 4,494 teachers working in Uşak province. To calculate the appropriate sample size representing the population, a theoretical sample size chart was used. The scales were administered by the researchers during on-site school visits. According to this chart, the sample of 476 teachers was selected from the 4,494 teachers working in schools in Uşak. To reach a sufficient sample size, 500 scales were distributed to the teachers, and 492 were returned completed. After examining the scales, 16 scales were excluded from the analysis due to incomplete responses or failure to follow the instructions, and the analysis continued with 476 valid scales. Personal information related to the sample is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Personal Information of the Sample

Variable		N	%
Gender	Female	225	47.3
	Male	241	52.7
Graduation	Associate's degree	8	1.7
	Bachelor's degree	381	80.0
	Graduate degree	87	18.3
Seniority (Years)	1-10 years	200	42.0
	11-20 years	180	37.8
	21-30 years	76	16.0
	31 years and above	20	4.2
Years of Service in the School (Years)	1-5 years	298	62.6
	6-10 years	111	23.3
	11 years and above	67	14.1
Number of Teachers in the School	1-10 teachers	17	3.6
	11-20 teachers	58	12.2
	21-30 teachers	138	29.0
	31 teachers and above	263	55,3

When examining Table 1 containing the personal data of the sample, it can be indicated that the number of female and male teachers is approximately equal. Most of the participants in the study are teachers with a bachelor's degree. When examining seniority, it is observed that teachers with 1-10 years of experience make up the majority. Regarding the years of service in the same school, the highest participation came from teachers who have been at the same school for 1-5 years. In terms of the number of teachers, those from schools with 31 or more teachers had the highest representation in the study.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

In the data collection process of the research, the Shared Leadership Perception Scale, Teacher Leadership Scale and Work Engagement Scale were used. The details of the scales are provided below.

Shared Leadership Perception Scale: The "Shared Leadership Perception" scale, developed by Wood (2005) and adapted into Turkish by Bostancı (2012), was used to measure teachers' perceptions of shared leadership. The scale consists of 4 dimensions and a total of 18 items: "task completion collectively (9 items)", "mutual skill development (2 items)", "decentralized interaction among employees (4 items)", and "emotional support (3 items)". The scale is a 4-point Likert type: "1=Strongly disagree; 2=Generally disagree; 3=Generally agree; 4=Strongly agree". In the adaptation study, Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients for the scale dimensions ranged from 0.74 to 0.88. The overall reliability coefficient of the scale was found to be 0.91. In this study, the reliability coefficients for the dimensions ranged from 0.71 to 0.93. The overall reliability coefficient for the scale was 0.93. To determine the suitability of the factor structure of the scale for the research, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted. The obtained fit indices ($\chi^2/df=3.055$; RMSEA=0.066; CFI=0.95; TLI=0.93; IFI=0.95) show that the factor structure of the scale is validated.

Teacher Leadership Scale: The "Teacher Leadership Scale," developed by Beycioğlu and Aslan (2010) to determine teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership, was used in this study. The scale consists of 3 dimensions and a total of 25 items: "Institutional development (9 items)", "Professional development (11 items)", and "Collaboration with colleagues (5 items)". The scale is a 5-point Likert type: "1=Never; 2=Rarely; 3=Sometimes; 4=Frequently; 5=Always". In the study where the scale was developed, Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients for the dimensions ranged from 0.87 to 0.92. The overall reliability coefficient of the scale was found to be 0.95. In this study, the reliability coefficients for the dimensions ranged from 0.89 to 0.92, and the overall reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.96. To determine the suitability of the factor structure of the scale for the research, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted. The obtained fit indices ($\chi^2/df=3.844$; RMSEA=0.077; CFI=0.93; TLI=0.90; IFI=0.92) indicate that the factor structure of the scale is validated.

Work Engagement Scale: The "Work Engagement Scale," developed by Schaufeli et al. (2002) and adapted by Turgut (2011) to determine teachers' levels of work engagement, was used in this study. The scale consists of 3 dimensions and a total of 17 items: "Vigor (6 items)", "Absorption (6 items)", and "Dedication (5 items)". The scale is a 6-point Likert type: "1=Never; 2=Rarely; 3=Sometimes; 4=Moderately; 5=Mostly; 6=Always". In the study where the scale was adapted, Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients for the dimensions ranged from 0.81 to 0.87, and the overall reliability was found to be 0.89. In this study, the reliability coefficients for the dimensions ranged from 0.83 to 0.93, and the overall reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.94. To determine the suitability of the factor structure of the scale for the research, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted. According to the analysis results, the fit indices ($\chi^2/df=4.273$; RMSEA=0.080; CFI=0.95; TLI=0.94; IFI=0.92) indicate that the factor structure of the scale is validated.

2.4. Data Analysis

In the research, the presence of missing data was first evaluated. After confirming that no missing data existed, the assumptions of multivariate normality, outliers, and multicollinearity were examined. In this context, the skewness and kurtosis coefficients were analyzed. Since the skewness and kurtosis values of all observed and latent variables were between +2 and -2, it was concluded that the data followed a normal distribution (Karagöz, 2016). Outliers were checked as they could potentially affect the significance of the

model. The Mardia coefficient and critical ratio value were examined to determine the presence of outliers. In the analysis of outliers, it is expected that the Mardia coefficient should be less than 1.96, and the critical ratio value should be less than 5. In this study, the Mardia coefficient was calculated as 1.86, and the critical ratio value was 3.6. Since the VIF values were found to be below 10 and the tolerance values were greater than 0.2, it was concluded that there was no multicollinearity problem among the variables. The VIF value for shared leadership and teacher leadership levels was calculated as 1.282, and the tolerance value was 0.780, confirming that there was no multicollinearity problem among the variables.

In the second phase of the research, confirmatory factor analyses were conducted to test the measurement model. For model fit, IFI, CFI, and TLI fit indices between 0.90 and 0.95 are considered acceptable, while values of 0.95 and above are evaluated as indicating good fit. An RMSEA value of less than 0.08 is considered a good fit (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu & Büyüköztürk, 2012). In the analysis, the fit index values showing the validity of the measurement model ($\chi^2/df=2.368$; RMSEA=0.054; CFI=0.91; TLI=0.90; IFI=0.91) indicated that the model was acceptable. Additionally, significant relationships were found among the measurement model variables: between shared leadership and teacher leadership ($r=0.48$), between teacher leadership and work engagement ($r=0.72$), and between shared leadership and work engagement ($r=0.46$). Pearson’s correlation was used to determine the relationship between the variables. To determine the mediating role of teacher leadership in the relationship between teachers' work engagement and shared leadership in schools, the Process Macro (Model 4) developed by Hayes (2022) was used.

3. Results

In the study, analyses were applied to the data that showed normal distribution based on skewness and kurtosis coefficients. Descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients for convergent and discriminant validity results were obtained. For convergent validity, AVE values were examined, and it was found that they were above 0.50. Therefore, it was concluded that convergent validity was established (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2022). Regarding discriminant validity, since the square roots of the AVE values were greater than the correlation values in the same row or column, it can be stated that discriminant validity was achieved (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The results of these analyses are presented in Table 2. When examining Table 2, a significant positive moderate-level relationship was observed between shared leadership and teacher leadership ($r=0.47$), as well as between shared leadership and work engagement ($r=0.38$). A positive moderate-level relationship was also found between teacher leadership and work engagement ($r=0.64$).

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis Results for the Research Variables

Research Variables	N	Mean	SD	AVE	1.	2.	3.
1. Shared Leadership	476	2.91	0.54	0.580	0.76 ⁺		
2. Teacher Leadership	476	3.81	0.66	0.576	0.47**	0.76 ⁺	
3. Work Engagement	476	4.77	0.75	0.604	0.38**	0.64**	0.78 ⁺

** $p < 0.01$ level of significance

+ AVE value square roots

To determine the mediating role of teacher leadership in the relationship between teachers' work engagement and shared leadership in schools, PROCESS Model 4 was used with 5000 bootstrapping samples and a 95% confidence interval (Hayes, 2022; cited in Bozkurt, 2023). The findings regarding the direct effect of shared leadership on work engagement and the mediating role of teacher leadership are presented in Table 3. According to Table 3, shared leadership has a significant and positive effect on work engagement behavior, meaning it is directly related ($\beta = 0.14$, $p < 0.001$). Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is supported. Furthermore, the analysis examining the mediating role of teacher leadership shows that the rela-

relationship between shared leadership and work engagement occurs through teacher leadership. The mediation effect ($\beta = 0.38, p < 0.001$) is statistically significant. These analysis results indicate that Hypothesis 2 is also supported.

Table 3. Unstandardized Total, Direct, and Indirect Effects of the Mediation Model

Effect	Estimate	SE	p	%95 Bootstrap CI	
				LL	UL
Direct Effects					
SLàTL	0.57	0.50	0.00	0.47	0.67
TL à WE	0.67	0.05	0.00	0.58	0.76
SLàWE	0.14	0.06	0.01	0.04	0.25
Indirect Effects					
SLàWE	0.38	0.06		0.27	0.50
Total Effects					
SLàWE	0.52	0.06	0.00	0.41	0.64

Figure 2. Mediation Model of Direct and Indirect Effects Between Variables

According to the results obtained from the structural mediation model in Figure 2, teacher leadership plays a mediating role in the relationship between shared leadership and work engagement. Shared leadership (Indirect Effect (IE) = 0.38; Confidence Interval (CI) [0.27; 0.50]) indirectly influences teachers' work engagement through teacher leadership. This is because the confidence interval values obtained from the bootstrap test analysis do not include zero (0) (Hayes, 2022; cited in Bozkurt, 2023).

4. Discussion

The study aimed to determine the mediating role of teacher leadership in the relationship between teachers' work engagement and shared leadership in schools. In recent years, the hierarchical leadership model in schools has gradually shifted towards the development of both formal and informal leadership structures, encouraging teachers to take on more responsibilities as leaders and contribute to the overall activities of the school (Zepeda, Mayers & Benson, 2013). In this sense, it is emphasized that schools need to make a significant shift from traditional leadership to shared leadership. Shared leadership is seen as a practice designed to create an environment for teacher leadership within the school (Wilhelm, 2013). The study has reached similar conclusions in line with this understanding. According to the research, there are positive, moderate-level relationships between shared leadership in schools and teacher

leadership. Shared leadership facilitates the creation and sharing of a process that forces everyone in the school community to become effective learning resources for each other and encourages collective learning (Mokoena, 2017). In a study conducted in a school with shared leadership, Wu, Cormican, and Chen (2018) found that teachers and administrators shared a common sense of purpose, supported each other, recognized individual and team contributions, and involved teachers in leadership roles during decision-making and constructive discussions. Therefore, the findings of this study align with the research results of Wu, Cormican, and Chen (2018) and other explanations in the literature.

According to the results of the study, teachers' perceptions of shared leadership significantly predict their perceptions of teacher leadership. In other words, shared leadership in schools influences teacher leadership. In their research, Harris and Muijs (2004) found that schools with more effective teacher leadership have a culture characterized by high levels of trust, collaboration, and partnership. It was determined that schools with high levels of teacher leadership create special opportunities and responsibilities for teacher leaders to fulfill their roles. Regardless of how formal leadership is organized in schools, teacher leadership should be supported by creating an environment where teachers can work together, share ideas and resources, and help their colleagues. Teachers should be empowered and given opportunities to develop their responsibilities and teacher leadership (Cheng & Szeto, 2016; Supovitz, 2018). Based on these findings, it can be said that shared leadership in schools can support teacher leadership. This is because, as seen in studies in the literature, shared leadership benefits schools by enhancing teacher leadership. According to Zepeda, Mayers and Benson (2013), when teachers are part of the decision-making process in schools, their sense of ownership of the school increases. Additionally, schools with shared leadership have positive effects on student learning, school development, and the school's capacity-building ability. Teacher leadership also helps in fostering collaborative leadership behavior between school leaders and teachers (Printy & Marks, 2006; Cheng & Szeto, 2016). Shared leadership, by nature, offers a more collaborative perspective on influence and authority. The hierarchical school structure also includes shared, collaborative, and parallel leadership roles that support the understanding of teacher leadership (Nappi, 2014). Especially, in recent years, the increasingly complex nature of schools and their operations has led to a constant emphasis on the need for more collaborative management, creating a school environment based on shared responsibility with teachers (Harris & Lambert, 2003; cited in Kılınç & Receptoğlu, 2013). All teachers have the capacity to be leaders, and leadership must be supported by the systems in which teachers work, with opportunities for teachers to participate in leadership roles both within and outside the school (Zepeda, Mayers & Benson, 2013; Uribe-Flórez, Al-Rawashdeh & Morales, 2014; Sawyer, Neel & Coulter, 2016). Hence, the idea of having shared leadership is vital to maximizing the effectiveness of teacher leadership initiatives. The rationale for shared leadership is based on the idea of sustainable school change and development (Uribe-Flórez, Al-Rawashdeh & Morales, 2014). The finding that shared leadership in schools enhances teachers' leadership skills has been shown not only by this study but also by research conducted by Boardman (2001). Boardman (2001) investigated shared leadership processes in Tasmanian schools and found that teachers discovered they were leaders (Kocolowski, 2010).

Additionally, the study found a positive moderate-level relationship between teacher leadership and work engagement. According to the research results, teachers' leadership skills significantly predict their work engagement. In other words, having leadership skills influences teachers' work engagement. Indeed, recent studies have similarly revealed that teachers' positive emotions influence their enthusiasm and dedication toward work through both direct and indirect pathways. For instance, in the study conducted by Burić and Moè (2020), it was found that teachers' positive emotions had both direct and indirect effects—mediated by self-efficacy and job satisfaction—on their level of enthusiasm for work. In shared leadership, employees take care of one another, show loyalty to each other and the organization, and try to develop and emotionally support each other (Wood, 2005). In a study conducted by Gokhale (2015), a relationship was found between career satisfaction and work engagement. In research by Sesen, Tabak, and Arli (2017), it was determined that teachers who internalize high levels of self-leadership behaviors have higher levels of school commitment, job satisfaction, self-assessment, self-motivation, and self-goal setting. It was shown that leadership behaviors have significant effects on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and innovation. Therefore, it can be seen that the results of this study align with the findings of the mentioned studies. Based on these explanations, as well as the results of the previous studies and this research, it can be stated that teacher leadership affects teachers' work engagement.

Another result of the study is that there is a positive moderate-level relationship between shared leadership and work engagement. Teachers' perceptions of shared leadership significantly predict their work engagement. According to a study by Bostancı, Gidiş, Uğurlu and Dilsiz (2018), a significant positive moderate-level relationship was also found between shared leadership and positive emotions toward work. Bruce (2012) highlighted that teachers' work engagement is crucial for achieving high levels of student success, noting that engaged teachers are enthusiastic and inspiring for students (cited in Khan, 2016). Teachers' work engagement should be supported by the school environment and structure (Bae, Song, Park & Kim, 2013). This is because work engagement is important. It has been found that engaged teachers improve student success and have no intention of leaving their jobs (Klassen, Aldhafri, Mansfield, Purwanto, Siu, Wong & Woods-McConney, 2012). In their research, Uslu and Beycioğlu (2013) found a moderate positive relationship between school administrators' shared leadership behaviors and teachers' organizational commitment levels. Ağıroğlu-Bakır and Aslan (2014) also found a significant, high-level positive relationship between teachers' perceptions of shared leadership and their perceptions of organizational commitment. Similarly, Sarıççek (2014) concluded that there was a positive moderate-level relationship between teachers' perceptions of shared leadership in schools and their work engagement and team spirit. Hulpia, Devos, and Rosseel (2009) also found that the implementation of shared leadership increased teachers' job satisfaction. Hence, in schools with shared leadership, results related to teachers' work engagement have been achieved. Based on the research results and literature explanations, it can be stated that shared leadership in schools affects teachers' work engagement.

Finally, the hypothesis that teacher leadership played a mediating role in the relationship between shared leadership in schools and teachers' work engagement was confirmed in the study. In other words, it was determined that teacher leadership had a mediating effect on how shared leadership in schools predicted the level of work engagement. In a study by Wu, Cormican, and Chen (2018), it was found that shared leadership increased levels of commitment and motivation among employees, positively affected job satisfaction, and increased employees' willingness to participate in leadership activities. In shared leadership, school administrators assign leadership and responsibility to teachers. In schools with shared leadership, as teachers gain new skills in a safe environment encouraged by their administrators, they grow as leaders and later apply these skills in their classrooms and collaborative team activities within the school. Shared leadership is a powerful way for school development because it makes teachers feel better and happier at work through their leadership roles (Wilhelm, 2013). In a study by Slavit, Kennedy, Deuel, and Nelson (2011), it was found that the implementation of shared leadership increased teachers' sense of professionalism and shared responsibility. Teacher leadership is developing competence by involving teachers in decision-making, strengthening them professionally, and increasing their responsibilities. For this, collaboration must be embedded in the school culture, and teacher leadership must be supported by involving teachers in managerial decisions and practices (Cheng & Szeto, 2016; Slavit, Kennedy, Deuel & Nelson, 2011; Nappi, 2014). According to Yılmaz (2013), shared leadership makes it easier for the school to achieve its goals, as school principals develop closer relationships with school members and foster genuine relationships. In this case, shared leadership is seen as important in increasing school success. Additionally, shared leadership facilitates group solidarity and reduces intra-group conflicts, which contributes to team success (Kocolowski, 2010). In his research, Yener (2016) found that shared leadership behaviors reduced turnover intentions and increased perceptions of psychological comfort. Based on the explanations and the mentioned studies, it can be concluded that shared leadership in schools increases teachers' work engagement, and the contribution of shared leadership to teacher leadership also plays a significant role in this effect.

As can be deduced from the research, it is clear that for schools to achieve their goals and ensure teachers' work engagement, shared leadership must be integrated into the school structure, and teacher leadership must be supported. The findings of this study, which identified that teacher leadership perceptions mediate the impact of teachers' perceptions of shared leadership on their work engagement, are consistent with research and studies in the literature and it is evident that this study supports those findings.

4.1. Limitations and implications

In the study, the hypotheses that shared leadership significantly positively predict work engagement behavior (H1) and that teacher leadership plays a mediating role in the relationship between shared leadership in schools and teachers' work engagement (H2) have been confirmed. However, the explanations regarding the relationships between the variables are limited compared to a qualitative study. In this research, data were collected quantitatively using scales. It was assumed that the responses to the scales were answered sincerely and correctly, which constitutes a limitation of the study. Additionally, this study only includes public schools. It would be beneficial to conduct a comparative study analyzing the relationships between variables based on the perceptions of teachers in non-public, private schools, as this would contribute to the literature.

Moreover, in this study, data were collected through self-report scales. The fact that participants reflected their own perceptions may involve certain internal bias risks, such as social desirability or cognitive biases related to response tendencies. This raises the possibility that the relationships among variables might yield different results when assessed using objective measurements.

Additionally, the study was conducted with a sample limited to the province of Uşak in Türkiye. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted with caution before being generalized to different geographical, cultural or administrative contexts. These limitations may be addressed in future studies conducted in various regions and with diverse samples.

4.2. Conclusions

In this study, the structural mediation model, which was developed based on the literature, confirming that teacher leadership perceptions mediate the impact of teachers' perceptions of shared leadership on their work engagement levels, was validated by using the obtained data set. Based on the results of the study, it is hoped that awareness will be raised among educational administrators and policymakers. While there are teacher councils, subject teacher groups, and branch teacher committees in Türkiye related to shared leadership and teacher leadership within the school structure, the continued influence of the centralized structure of the Ministry of National Education has an adverse effect on teachers' work engagement. Based on the study's results, it can be suggested that to increase the work engagement of teachers, who play a key role in achieving school goals, schools should legally integrate the functioning of shared leadership into their structure and provide opportunities for teacher leadership.

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